

ATLANTIC
— CENTRE —

**GEOPOLITICS AND
COOPERATION IN THE
SOUTH ATLANTIC**

Atlantic Centre

Geopolitics and Cooperation in the South Atlantic

Lisbon, 2024

Title

Geopolitics and Cooperation in the South Atlantic

Author

Murilo Gomes da Costa

Editor

Atlantic Centre

Production

Atlantic Centre and Murilo Gomes da Costa

Layout and Graphic Design

Núcleo de Design da Secretaria-Geral do Ministério de Defesa Nacional de Portugal

Text Review

Atlantic Centre

August, 2024

Summary

Introduction

Brazil

Portugal

Zopacas

CPLP

Extra-regional presence

UN Ocean Decade

7

8

12

15

17

19

22

Preface

In an era marked by geopolitical unpredictability, the global stage is witnessing increasing poses significant challenges to the stability and security of nations worldwide.

The current geopolitical landscape can be seen as a complex web of contrasting interests, power scuffles, and rising tensions. From the resurgence of great power competition to the proliferation of non-state actors and the enhancement of regional conflicts, instability looms large over the global arena. In that respect, as an example, the current affairs in the Red Sea highlight how increasing insecurity on regional playing fields, assumes a transnational and interdependent expression where local and regional phenomena deliver a myriad of impacts on world affairs.

In this context, multilateralism assumes a renewed significance. At its core, multilateralism embodies the principle of collective action, recognizing that many of the challenges we face today – from regional conflicts, illicit activities associated with organised crime, with an impact on maritime security, to climate change – transcend national borders. This requires concerted efforts on the part of the international community, in an increasingly interconnected world.

In addition, the resurgence of Atlantic territorialization, with States' political aspirations in extending and expanding their continental shelf adds a new dimension to the appeal of multi-lateral cooperation. These competing visions of world order and diverging national interests, albeit politically legitimate, may hinder efforts to forge consensus among States.

Furthermore, as the transatlantic community confronts itself with an array of geopolitical challenges – from assertiveness and expansionism in the East and the erosion of ecosystems and communities throughout the Atlantic –, the imperative of strengthening ties across the Atlantic community has never been more pressing.

However, in the face of these challenges, it remains recognised that the attractive force based on cooperation and the search for consensus transcends the narrow confines of national interests, and rivalries. As nations grapple with a significant set of challenges, risks and threats, collective collaborative action becomes increasingly self-evident. By embracing the commitment to cooperation and political dialogue, a path towards a more stable, prosperous, and peaceful Atlantic can be charted.

In that regard, winner of the FLAD Atlantic Security Award 2022, Dr. Murilo Gomes da Costa presents that same analysis, and as States confront the plethora of challenges facing the world today, the reaffirmation and commitment to international security cooperation can pose autonomously as a valuable tool to decrease the impending feeling of insecurity in the Atlantic. This booklet highlights, through extensive Cartographic resources, the several cooperative relationships developed on the South Atlantic and to what extent can those regional dynamics alter security in the Atlantic at large.

Through international cooperation, the Atlantic community can navigate the complexities of the 21st century through a more collaborative way and build a more resilient and inclusive international order: A Whole of Atlantic community.

Nuno de Noronha Bragança

Rear Admiral
Atlantic Centre Coordinator

Introduction

Since the end of the Cold War, several bilateral initiatives and multilateral organizations, such as the Zone of Peace and Cooperation of the South Atlantic (ZOPACAS), the Community of Portuguese Language Countries (CPLP), and the African Union, have contributed to the consolidation of the South Atlantic as a Zone of Peace and Cooperation. However, the region's potential for strategic and economic growth continues to attract geopolitical interest.

A central element in this process of promoting peace and cooperation has been the strengthening of the field of International Development Cooperation (IDC). IDC is considered a foreign policy tool in the academic literature, although not all governments see the relevance and appropriateness of robust cooperation programs in the same way. Especially in the context of issues such as peace and cooperation, **international defense cooperation** becomes a tool for strengthening the material, technical and scientific capacities of the countries of the South.

The objective of this booklet is to present a collection of thematic defence cartography images of the South Atlantic, with a focus on international initiatives. This document is a publication of the project "**The Potential of Defense Cooperation in the South Atlantic**" winner of the **FLAD Atlantic Security Award 2022**, promoted by the National Defense Institute (IDN), the Luso-American Development Foundation (FLAD), and the Atlantic Centre.

An innovation of the project is the use of **thematic cartography** made possible by the collection of data and the creation of original images such as maps, graphs, and timelines, which will be publicly available. The development is the responsibility of the project author in collaboration with the **Cartography Team of the World Political Analysis Laboratory (LABMUNDO)**, a research center located at the Institute of Social and Political Studies of the State University of Rio de Janeiro (IESP-UERJ). Some of the images presented here were originally published in the Atlas of Brazilian Defense Politics and are freely available in the [LABMUNDO Map Library](#).

Murilo Gomes da Costa

PhD in Political Science (IESP - UERJ)

Researcher at the [World Political Analysis Laboratory \(LABMUNDO\)](#)

FLAD Atlantic Security Award 2022 Research Fellow

BRAZIL

Collection of images on Brazil's role in the South Atlantic, with emphasis on its expanded strategic surrounding

GEOPOLITICAL STRATEGIC ENVIRONMENT

Immediate geopolitical surroundings of Brazil, according to denition by Brazilian Armed Forces

The geographical demarcation of the Brazilian strategic surrounding consists of two areas: The first is the immediate strategic surrounding, which includes all the countries located in South America and the Brazilian jurisdictional territory at sea - the Blue Amazon, which also includes the Brazilian islands in the ocean.

The second area encompasses the extended strategic surrounding, which includes the South Atlantic, the African countries bordering the ocean, and Antarctic. The inclusion of Antarctic, at the southernmost part of the South Atlantic region, is due to its importance to Brazil, both for the development of technical and scientific research and for the consolidation of a presence throughout the South Atlantic.

BRAZIL

Collection of images on Brazil's role in the South Atlantic, with emphasis on its expanded strategic surrounding

LAST FRONTIER AT SEA

Dimension of Green and Blue Amazon area, in km², in 2016

Due to the Brazilian maritime region covering an area equivalent to 52% of the terrestrial territory - with dimensions and biodiversity similar to that of the Amazon Rainforest, also known as the “Green Amazon” in military circles - it has been conventionally named the Blue Amazon or “**Ama-zônia Azul**”.

In 2015, the Dilma government established the **National Day of the Blue Amazon** through Act No. 13.187. The date was chosen to commemorate the entry into force of the **United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)** on November 16, 1994.

The Blue Amazon encompasses a wide range of valuable resources and strategic assets. In recent decades, there has been an increase in investments for the discovery and exploitation of resources in the sea.

The areas that have received the most investments are linked to industry, infrastructure, as well as projects in the fields of science and technology. These research investments enable better tracking of the potential resources in the sea and the development of effective and sustainable means of exploiting these resources.

WEALTHIES OF THE BLUE AMAZON

Mapping of main minerals in the seabed of Brazilian coast, in 2016

Quantity of known species in the marine biodiversity of the Blue Amazon, in 2016

Plantae Kingdom Phylum

Labmurdo, 2018

BRAZIL

Chronology of Claims for the expansion of the “Blue Amazon”

CHRONOLOGY OF CLAIMS FOR THE EXPANSION OF THE "BLUE AMAZON"

Evolution of Brazil's claims for the extension of the outer limits of the Brazilian continental shelf, beyond 200 miles, between 2004 and 2024

2004

Brazil submitted the "Proposal for the Outer Limit of the Brazilian Continental Shelf beyond two hundred miles" to the UN CLCS

2007

The Commission's Recommendations were as follows: out of the 960,000 km² of area claimed by Brazil (beyond the 200 nautical miles), the CLCS did not agree with approximately 190,000 km²

2007

Brazil decided not to accept the recommendation. The CIRM proposed a process to review the initial proposal.

2008

On May 13th, during its 168th Ordinary Session, the Interministerial Commission for Marine Resources (CIRM) of Brazil decided to prepare a Revised Proposal for the Outer Limit of the Brazilian Continental Shelf beyond the two hundred nautical miles, which will be duly submitted to the CLCS in due course

2008

On July 4th, the new Proposal was approved by the Presidency of the Republic. With the revised proposal, the Brazilian continental margin was divided into three distinct areas:
-Southern Region
-Equatorial Margin
-Eastern/Southern Margin

2015

The proposal for the Southern Region, located within part of the Southern Margin, was submitted to the United Nations in April 2015 and presented to the Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf on August 25

2017

The proposal for the Equatorial Margin was submitted to the United Nations on September 8

2018

The proposal for the Equatorial Margin was presented at the Plenary Meeting of the Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf on March 8th

2018

The proposal for the Eastern/Southern Margin, including the Rio Grande Rise (RGR), was submitted to the United Nations on December 7. With the inclusion of the RGR in this submission, the Blue Amazon will extend to an area of approximately 5.7 million km²

2019

In March, the CLCS fully approved the proposed Outer Limit put forth by Brazil regarding the Southern Region, thus incorporating an area of approximately 170,000 km² into the Continental Shelf

2019

The analysis of the "Equatorial Margin Proposal" took place in August, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it has been on hold since February 2020.

2024

Due to the delay caused by the suspension of the analysis of the Equatorial Margin, it is likely that the consideration of the Eastern/Southern Margin Proposal, including the Rio Grande Rise (RGR), will commence from 2024 onwards.

2004

2008

2012

2016

2020

2024

Source: Marinha do Brasil (2023)

In the context of legal discussions on maritime law, **the expansion of states' maritime boundaries** is one of the most relevant topics in the international arena.

In Brazil, there has been significant progress in the legal procedures for the expansion of the Brazilian maritime boundary, which has been formalized through the **Brazilian Continental Shelf Survey Plan (LEPLAC)** since 1987.

Since the establishment of LEPLAC, the **Interministerial Commission for Marine Resources (CIRM)** of Brazil has submitted various proposals to the **UN Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf (CLCS)**, as depicted in the image, for the expansion of the Brazilian maritime territory. If the CLCS approves all the pending claims, the “Blue Amazon” will extend to approximately 5.7 million km².

BRAZIL

Defense Cooperation in the South Atlantic

DEFENCE COOPERATION IN THE SOUTH ATLANTIC

Bilateral agreements in the field of Defense and Military Affairs signed between Brazil and African countries or ZOPACAS member countries, between 1990 and 2023

Source: Divisão de Acordos Internacionais do Itamaraty, 2023 e Lima; Milani; Duarte; Gomes da Costa, et al., 2017

*Obs: This figure updates the data from the image "Defence in the Expanded Strategic Environment," originally published in the Atlas of Brazilian Defense Policy.

Among the highlighted defense cooperation actions in this image, particular emphasis should be given to military training. In **Guinea-Bissau, a Center for Security Forces Training** was established with Brazilian investment of approximately 3 million dollars. Similarly, in **Namibia**, the Brazilian government provided support for the **creation of the Marine Corps**, consisting of approximately 600 military personnel, along with the donation of vessels.

Another significant initiative was the **surveying of Namibia's continental shelf**. In the case of **Guinea-Bissau**, Brazil provided support for security sector reform through the United Nations, with an investment of around 750,000 dollars between 2004 and 2005.

PORTUGAL

Portugal's Cooperation Agreements in the South Atlantic

PORTUGAL'S COOPERATION AGREEMENTS IN THE SOUTH ATLANTIC

Number of military technical cooperation agreements in force between Portugal and countries in the South Atlantic between 1990 and 2021

Portugal's engagement with the countries of the South Atlantic was not limited to Brazil alone. Portuguese involvement was solidified through numerous Cooperation Framework Programs signed with Angola, Cape Verde, Guinea-Bissau, São Tomé and Príncipe, among others.

The portuguese international cooperation framework programs in the South Atlantic encompass projects of a technical-military nature, focused on maritime security aspects and the creation of conditions for joint participation of the Portuguese Armed Forces and the aforementioned countries in peacekeeping and humanitarian missions.

PORTUGAL

Portugal's Defence Cooperation in the Atlantic

PORTUGAL'S DEFENCE COOPERATION IN THE ATLANTIC

Overall Defence Cooperation expenditure between Portugal and African South Atlantic Countries, in euros, in 2020

Source: Ministério da Defesa Nacional de Portugal (2020).

The financial obligations arising from projects included in the **Cooperation Framework Programs in the Defense** domain are part of Portugal's eligible contribution to **Official Development Assistance (ODA)**. In addition to the four countries located in the South Atlantic, Portugal also allocates resources for the implementation of cooperation projects with other countries of the Community of Portuguese Language Countries (CPLP), such as Mozambique and Timor-Leste.

Projects with **Cape Verde** are focused on the "Higher Structure of the Armed Forces" and "Maritime Security and State Authority at Sea". In **Guinea-Bissau**, the resources aim to support the "Reform of the higher structure of the Armed Forces". In **São Tomé and Príncipe**, the resources are invested in the "Higher Defense Structure and Armed Forces," "Coast Guard," and "Military Engineering Construction Platoon." In Angola, they are allocated to the "Higher National Defense and Armed Forces Structure," "Army," "National Air Force," "Navy," and "Higher War School."

PORTUGAL

Chronology of Atlantic Centre Activities

CHRONOLOGY OF THE ATLANTIC CENTRE

Main activities developed by the Atlantic Centre between 2018 and 2023

Source: República Portuguesa - Defesa Nacional, 2023

Another significant action undertaken by Portugal was the **launch of the "Atlantic Centre" (AC) initiative** as a multilateral center of excellence aimed at promoting defense capability development. The initiative was officially launched on May 14, 2021, and since then has had an intense agenda of annual activities.

The latest Atlantic Center joint declaration was signed by 23 nations¹. The AC is a key diplomatic forum for uniting North-South interests, establishing an important platform for "pan-Atlantic" dialogue and cooperation.

¹ Angola, Brazil, Cape Verde, Cameroon, Colombia, Denmark, Equatorial Guinea, France, Gambia, Germany, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Morocco, Netherlands, Nigeria, Portugal, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Spain, Togo, United Kingdom, United States of America, Uruguay.

SOUTH ATLANTIC PEACE AND COOPERATION ZONE (ZOPACAS)

Collection of images about the South Atlantic Peace and Cooperation Zone (Zopacas)

CREATION OF SOUTH ATLANTIC PEACE AND COOPERATION ZONE

Votes by country on the General Assembly's 41/11s Resolution in 1986, that created the Zopacas

Established on October 27, 1986, ZOPACAS was created through **United Nations General Assembly Resolution 41/11** with the aim of promoting regional cooperation and maintaining peace and security in the surrounding areas of the South American countries and the western coast of Africa that have joined the initiative.

Ministerial meetings address various topics, including cooperation in peace and security, defense, economic development and financial issues, oceans and marine resources, climate change, transportation and communications, prevention and combating of international crime and terrorism, among others.

SOUTH ATLANTIC PEACE AND COOPERATION ZONE (ZOPACAS)

Collection of images about the South Atlantic Peace and Cooperation Zone (Zopacas)

ZOPACAS MINISTERIAL MEETINGS

Chronology of ministerial meetings between Zopacas member states, by date and location, between 1988 and 2023

Source: Marinha do Brasil (2020) and ONU (2021)

Since its creation, ZOPACAS has experienced periods of both intensification and suspension of its international activities. As illustrated in the figure, the main ministerial meetings of the signatory countries took place between 1988 and 2013.

In July 2021, marking the 35th anniversary of ZOPACAS, **Resolution A/RES/75/312 was approved during the 75th Session of the United Nations** General Assembly, shedding new light on the need to resume Ministerial Meetings.

The definitive resumption of ZOPACAS ministerial meetings, after a decade-long hiatus, took place in April 2023. On this occasion, for the next two years, Cape Verde assumed the role of coordinator of Zopacas. **Brazil proposed to host the IX Ministerial Meeting in 2026**, commemorating the 40th anniversary of ZOPACAS' establishment.

Community of Portuguese Language Countries (CPLP)

Collection of images on CPLP initiatives in international cooperation

CPLP SPECIAL FUND FOR INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

Financial Execution of Cooperation Activities under the CPLP Special Fund, by type of activity, and by amount requested from the fund, in millions of euros

Activities carried out between 2000 and 2019

Activities carried out in 2020

Source: CPLP (2023)

Within the CPLP cooperation framework, the XIII Conference of Heads of State and Government of the CPLP, held in Luanda on July 16, 2021, approved the “**Resolution on the Definition of a New Strategic Orientation for CPLP Cooperation**” This resolution aimed to accelerate the CPLP’s contribution to the **UN’s 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development**. The figure illustrates the increase in the absolute amount requested from the fund when comparing only the year 2020 with the cumulative budget executed from 2000 to 2019.

CPLP actions focused on the oceans gained prominence in 2016 with the III Meeting of Ministers of Maritime Affairs held in Dili. During this meeting, the first **CPLP Action Plan for maritime affairs** was approved. This plan prioritizes the implementation of the following initiatives:

- Establishment of the CPLP Maritime Studies Center;
- Atlas of Coastal and Oceanic Zones of CPLP Countries;
- Extension of the continental shelf and associated projects;
- International Projection of the CPLP through the Oceans;
- Development of Maritime Clusters;
- CPLP Portal for Maritime Affairs;
- CPLP Partnership for Marine Litter.

Community of Portuguese Language Countries (CPLP)

Collection of images on CPLP initiatives in international cooperation

DEFENCE COOPERATION AT THE CPLP

Hosts and projects of the Community of Portuguese Language Countries, between 2000 and 2016

Source: Ministry of Defence website, 2016; CPLP website, 2016; Portugal Armed Forces website, 2016.

Labmundo, 2018

The CPLP member countries have also developed initiatives in the area of defense cooperation. Regarding maritime security, cooperation issues have been discussed during the CPLP Meeting of Ministers of Maritime Affairs. The figure indicates the main headquarters and projects developed by the various countries belonging to the community. Initiatives include inter-ministerial meetings in the defense sector, joint military operations, and seminars with the presence of academics and

civilian and military authorities, reinforcing the dimension of cooperation and information exchange between civilians and the military.

At the last meeting of CPLP Ministers of National Defense, held on May 30, 2023, in Angola, the first annual monitoring of the Action Plan to advance implementation of **UN Resolution 1325** was presented, focusing on the theme “**Women, Peace, and Security.**”

EXTRA-REGIONAL PRESENCE

Collection of images on the actions of extra-regional powers in the South Atlantic, with an emphasis on the UK, USA and France

GLOBAL ROLE OF U.S. MILITARY AND NAVAL POWER

Areas of responsibility for the six land-based geographic combatant commands and identification of the approximate areas of operation of the US Fleets.

Source: WikimediaCommons (2022)

The U.S. presence in the South Atlantic is manifested through three categories of action: the reestablishment of the U.S. Fourth Fleet in July 2008, the strengthening of the United States Southern Command (SOUTHCOM), and the creation of the United States Africa Command (AFRICOM) in October 2008.

For the first time, the U.S. had a military structure comprising six Unified Combatant Commands and six Fleets worldwide.

As depicted in the figure above, the Fourth Fleet is responsible for the security of South America and the South Atlantic, encompassing the ships, submarines, and aircraft that defend the area under the USSOUTHCOM's responsibility.

The official stated objective of the Fourth Fleet is to enhance cooperation and partnership with countries in the region through five missions: support for peacekeeping operations, humanitarian assistance, disaster relief, traditional maritime exercises, and countering drug operations.

As for AFRICOM, it was established by the United States² in 2006. One of the reasons for its creation was the keen pursuit of strategic resources. During that period, the U.S. sought to increase its import of oil from a vital area of interest, the Gulf of Guinea, located on the African coast.

² AFRICOM primarily operates in the Gulf of Guinea, but its jurisdiction encompasses 53 African countries, excluding Egypt.

EXTRA-REGIONAL PRESENCE

Collection of images on the actions of extra-regional powers in the South Atlantic, with an emphasis on the UK, USA and France

UK OVERSEAS TERRITORIES IN THE SOUTH ATLANTIC

Geopolitical configuration of the South Atlantic, with emphasis on the maritime zones under Brazilian jurisdiction and the jurisdiction and the Overseas Territories of the United Kingdom

Throughout its history, the United Kingdom has established a notable territorial presence in the South Atlantic Basin, granting it a unique strategic capacity that surpasses even the coastal countries of this ocean.

The figure illustrates the main British Overseas Territories, providing an overview of the extensive presence of British defense forces in the geopolitical landscape of the South Atlantic. In certain islands, such as Ascension, joint military activities are conducted with the United States.

EXTRA-REGIONAL PRESENCE

Collection of images on the actions of extra-regional powers in the South Atlantic, with an emphasis on the UK, USA and France

MILITARY FOREIGN PRESENCE IN SOUTH AMERICA

Extra-regional powers' presence via military bases with extraterritorial jurisdiction, military operations and military cooperation agreements, in 2016

In addition to France's interests and influence in Africa, France also has a presence in the South Atlantic due to its possession of French Guiana. The territory was a French colony until 1946 when it became a French overseas department.

The figure illustrates the presence of multiple extraregional actors in the Brazilian Strategic Surrounding. It highlights some of the military bases with extraterritorial status that play a strategic role in the region, notably the United States, France, and the United Kingdom.

UN Ocean Decade

Collection of images on initiatives under the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, with a focus on Africa

RESOLUTION "OCEANS AND THE LAW OF THE SEA"

Country votes on Resolution 72/73 of 2017, "Oceans and the Law of the Sea", adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, proclaiming the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development

Source: United Nations Digital Library (2023).

In 2017, the United Nations General Assembly proclaimed the **Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development** through Resolution (A/RES/72/73). The aim of the initiative, to be implemented between 2021 and 2030, is to take action to fulfill the commitments of the 2030 Agenda, with a particular focus on SDG 14 (Life Below Water - the conservation and sustainable use of oceans, seas and marine resources) and related goals. The initiative brings together scientists, governments, non-governmental organizations, and civil society in a collective effort to address ocean-related challenges and promote sustainable

development and the conservation of marine resources. The international coordination is carried out by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), which is also responsible for developing the Decade's Implementation Plan.

In 2022, Resolution **A/RES/77/248 - Oceans and the Law of the Sea** was approved by 159 votes in favor, 1 against, and 3 abstentions, representing significant progress compared to the initial adherence in 2017.

UN Ocean Decade

Collection of images on initiatives under the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, with a focus on Africa

AFRICAN PROJECTS RESULTING FROM THE "CALL FOR ACTIONS OF THE OCEAN DECADE"

Main Ocean Decade projects led by African organisations and/or states, between 2020 e 2023

Enhancement of Hydrographic and Oceanographic Observations

National Commission for Education, Sciences and Culture, Kingdom of Morocco (MarocNatCom)

Morocco

Ocean Literacy Educational Program

Ministry of Maritime Economy of Cape Verde

Cape Verde

West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use

Cape Verde Graduate School on Climate Change and Marine Sciences

Benin

Nigeria

African Youths Sustainable Ocean Campaign (AYSOC)

The Atlantic Maritime Academy Nigeria (Institute of Nautical Studies and Ocean Research)

Ocean to climate seamless forecasting in Africa (OSFiA)

Institut de Recherches Halieutiques et Océanologiques du Bénin (IRHOB)

Institutional capacity building towards the sustainability of ocean science in light of COVID-19 pandemic

Nipe Fagio

Low cost real-time monitoring of pollutants and water quality along the coral reefs in Tanzania

Aqua Farms Organization

Protecting the estuaries of Indic Ocean region

School of Aquatic Sciences and Fisheries Technology

Tanzania

Sustainable Ocean Management Education Programme

Ministry of Fisheries and Blue Economy

Seychelles

Mauritius

Fenoy-X

WIO Early Career Scientists Network

South Africa

Enhancing ocean observing system within The Republic of Mauritius

Mauritius Meteorological Services

No. of projects

Source: UNESCO-IOC (2022) and OCEANDECADE (2023)

So far, the implementation of the 'Ocean Decade' in the African continent lags behind many other regions of the world. The results of the first **Call for Actions of the Decade (No. 01/2020)** led to the endorsement of over 160 Ocean Decade Actions in the form of programs, projects, and contributions, concentrated in Europe and North America.

However, several African countries and organizations are involved in programs and initiatives, either as partners and/or as key actors in their implementation, as illustrated in the image.

REFERENCES & FURTHER READINGS

Costa, Wanderley Messias da. (2014). Projeção do Brasil no atlântico sul: geopolítica e estratégia. **Revista USP**, n°.95, p.9-22.

Costa, Murilo Gomes da. (2022). **Trajetórias que se encontram: Análise comparativa da inserção do Brasil e da África do Sul em seus Entornos Regionais (1998-2018)**. 2022. 413f. Tese (Doutorado em Ciência Política) – Instituto de Estudos Sociais e Políticos, Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro.

Costa, Murilo Gomes da. (2023) Desafios da Revitalização da Zona de Paz e Cooperação do Atlântico Sul no Contexto da Década Oceânica (2021-2030). Alantic Centre - **Policy Brief - Issue 16**, April

CPLP (2023). **Quadro de Execução do Fundo Especial**. URL: <https://www.cplp.org/id-3034.aspx>

Duarte, R. S. Costa, Murilo Gomes da. (2022). **A cooperação internacional brasileira em defesa como indutor de inovações**. In Amorim, O.; Azevedo, F (org). Estudos de defesa Inovação, estratégia e desenvolvimento industrial . Rio de Janeiro: FGV. 1 ed.

Lima, Maria Regina Soares de Lima; Milani, Carlos R. S; Duarte, Rubens de S. Duarte; Gomes da Costa, M. et al. (2017). **Atlas da política brasileira de defesa**. Buenos Aires: Clacso; Rio de Janeiro: Latitude Sul. 2017.

Marinha do Brasil. (2023). Plano de Levantamento da Plataforma Continental Brasileira (LE-PLAC). URL: <https://www.marinha.mil.br/secirm/pt-br/leplac>

Ministério da Defesa Nacional de Portugal. (2023). **Anuário Estatístico da Defesa Nacional - 2020**. URL: https://www.defesa.gov.pt/pt/defesa/dn/edn/Lists/PDEFINTER_DocumentoLookupList/AEDN-2020_VF.pdf

Ministério Público de Portugal (2023). **Consulta por Instrumentos Internacionais**. URL: <https://www.ministeriopublico.pt/tratados/resultados?ti=714>

Ocean Decade (2023). United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. **Decade Actions**. URL: <https://forum.oceandecade.org>

Organização das Nações Unidas (ONU). **Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 29 July 2021. A/RES/75/312.** Nova Iorque: United Nations General Assembly. 2021.

República Portuguesa. (2023). Ministério da Defesa Nacional. **The Atlantic Centre.** Lisboa, Portugal. URL: <https://www.defesa.gov.pt/pt/pdefesa/ac/about>

UNESCO-IOC (2022). The United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021–2030. **Ocean Decade Africa Roadmap.** Paris, UNESCO. (The Ocean Decade Series, 36).

United Nations Digital Library. (2023). Oceans and the law of the sea: resolution (adopted by the General Assembly in 2017). URL: <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/1325850?ln=en>

Institutional and financial support

The preparation of this booklet was financially supported by the **FLAD Atlantic Security Award 2022** of the Luso-American Development Foundation, the Atlantic Centre and the National Defense Institute. The content of this document is the responsibility of the author. It therefore does not represent the institutional view or position of the Luso-American Development Foundation (FLAD), the Atlantic Centre or the National Defense Institute (IDN).

FLAD
LUSO-AMERICAN
DEVELOPMENT FOUNDATION

ATLANTIC
— CENTRE —

idn Instituto
da Defesa Nacional

IESP. UERJ
Instituto de Estudos Sociais e Políticos

LABMUNDO